

EFFECT OF FLUID-STRUCTURE INTERACTION ON COMPOSITE STRUCTURAL VIBRATION

Y. W. Kwon^{1*}, E. M. Priest¹, J. H. Gordis¹

¹ Dept. of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Naval Postgraduate School, Monterey, USA

* Corresponding author (ywkwon@nps.edu)

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1 Introduction

Recently, there has been an increase in their use for marine applications. Polymer composites have strength and stiffness on the same order as aluminum and steel but are much lighter in comparison. This makes the craft much faster through the water and more fuel-efficient than its metallic counterparts. Furthermore, as evidenced by many steel craft, corrosion is a major factor in the lifespan of a ship. Many studies are being conducted to combat the corrosion caused by seawater and large temperature gradients encountered in daily operations [1]. Composites provide a reliable solution to this problem given that they do not corrode or decay and can remain in the water throughout their long life. However, there has been limited testing of composites in regard to reliability and durability over many years of rigorous open ocean operations. One of the aspects to be considered for composite ship structures is the effect of Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI).

The FSI can be interpreted as an added mass effect as well as added fluid damping to vibrating structures when in contact with a fluid medium such as water. The added mass effect changes the dynamic responses of the vibrating structure such as decreasing the natural frequencies. Analytical approaches to determine the natural frequencies with the added mass effect were based on the assumption that the mode shapes do not change with FSI while the frequencies change [2-5].

The effect of FSI is especially significant regarding a polymer composite structure since its density is close to the density of water. Studies of polymer composites under low velocity impact have shown that there is an increase in impact force with samples tested while in contact with water due to the added mass effect with the fluid medium [6-8]. The studies also have shown that the natural frequencies

of polymer composite plates, when in contact with water, decrease by approximately one-third of those tested in air. Furthermore, the difference between measured strains with and without FSI varies significantly from location to location of composite structures under impact loading.

The objective of this study is to further understand the vibrational characteristics of composite structures under the influence of FSI. To this end, multiple experimental studies were conducted for composite beam structures. The composite beams were investigated under clamped-free (cantilever) and free-free boundary conditions, both in air and fully submerged in water, respectively. The study contained herein utilizes two experimental techniques. First, the Digital Image Correlation (DIC) technique measures the free vibration response of a cantilever beam subjected to an initial disturbance. Second, Experimental Modal Analysis (EMA) is performed for a free-free beam using an impact hammer and accelerometers to determine its vibrational frequencies and modes of vibration. As well, the use of a high speed camera (HSC) system provides real time images of the free vibration response of the composite beams.

2 Test Specimens and Equipment

2.1 DIC Setup

Careful attention was made when setting up and adjusting the stereoscopic Charge-Coupled Device (CCD) cameras. The CCDs are attached to a vertical mounting beam attached to a tripod. This allows for adjustments relative to the mechanism in which the composite is being tested, ensuring the proper focal length to acquire clear images. The mounting beam also allows for the CCDs to be spaced symmetrically about the specimen in order to

achieve the proper stereo angle. The stereo angle is based on the type of lens being used. Here, 35mm lenses are used which require a stereo angle of at least 20°, with 60° being the absolute limit. All calculations for spacing requirements in this setup use a stereo angle of 25°. Simple geometry can be used to determine these requirements; however, testing the composite beams in water brings forth a couple of aspects that cannot be overlooked. The aspects to be considered are image magnification, and light refraction and reflection as discussed below.

Due to refraction, the water medium enlarges the image captured in DIC testing. According to Ref. [9], the degree to which the composite beam is magnified can be calculated using the following equation:

$$M = m \left\{ \frac{[1 + (d + R) / D]}{[1 + m(d + R) / D]} \right\} \quad (1)$$

with $R = 0.8$ and $m = 1.33$. Here, R is the radius of curvature for the camera lens, m is the index of refraction for water, D is the distance from the beam to the Plexiglas, and d is the distance from the camera to the Plexiglas. Those distances are measured in *cm* for Eq. (1). Then, M is the image magnification. Adjustments were made in order to capture the length of the beam. The final distance between the composite beam and the camera was determined to be 76.84*cm*. Since the distance D is equal to 29.85*cm*, the cameras were set to a distance d equal to 46.99*cm* from the tank. This yields an image magnification of 1.138. Therefore, the composite beam appears to be approximately 13.8% larger in water than in air for each CCD. This equates to an apparent beam length of 23.11*cm*. This is valid assuming the initial displacement of the beam is small.

To eliminate the reflection of light from the free surface of the water, the CCD cameras were aligned vertically from one another on the mounting beam in order to capture images from the side of the water tank. As well, the lighting system consisting of two *Lowell Pro* lights was placed at angles from below the waterline to achieve a uniform spread across the composite beam. This essentially eliminated all of the reflected light to the CCDs. Light refraction through the Plexiglas and water also affects the stereo angle of the system. Achieving the desired

stereo angle is accomplished through the use of Snell's Law which states:

$$n_1 \sin(\theta_1) = n_2 \sin(\theta_2) \quad (2)$$

where the subscripts one and two represent the initial medium from which the light originates and the secondary medium through which light refracts.

Solving for either θ_1 or θ_2 for light passing from a water medium into Plexiglas and then from the Plexiglas to air allows for the determination of the initial and final stereo angles. To achieve the desired minimum 25° stereo angle, the relative stereo angle of the CCD's must be 33.4°. The operational set up, with all adjustments being complete, is shown in Fig. 1.

2.2 Modal Analysis Setup

Since this test was conducted in air as well as while submerged in water, the accelerometers needed to be waterproofed prior to any tests being conducted. Since the impact hammer could not be reasonably waterproofed, a steel rod was used as an intermediate medium between the impact hammer and the beam specimen. The validity of this technique is discussed in Section 3.

Following the fabrication of the composite beams and waterproofing of the test equipment, ten accelerometers were evenly spaced and attached to the underside of the test beam. The impact hammer and accelerometer outputs were routed to a digital signal analyzer for data acquisition and analysis. The test beam was held by flexible lines at both ends to represent a free-free beam. For testing in water, the test beams were leveled in the center of the water level in the tank.

2.3 Composite Specimens

The composite beam test samples were constructed using the vacuum assisted resin transfer molding technique to mimic the technique used in marine construction. Two kinds of composite specimens were fabricated. The first kind consists of varying layers of non-biased, plain weave 6 ounce E-glass laid at both 0°/90° and +45°/- 45° orientations. The vinyl ester resin used for this process was Derakane 510A-40 epoxy and was cured at room temperature for 24 hours followed by two hours at 120°C. Table 1 provides an overview of the composite sample dimensions being used in this study. These samples were tested using the DIC technique.

The E-glass composite samples are flexible so that they are good to measure the vibrational motion using DIC. However, they are not suitable for experimental modal analysis where accelerometers need to be attached. This requires a much stiffer beam. As a result, a carbon composite beam was fabricated using TORAY T700CF carbon fiber weave. The same resin and fabrication technique was used. The carbon beam specimen is 25.1mm wide, 4.47mm high and 461mm long.

Several samples of each ply orientation were tested using the DIC technique. When subjected to an initial disturbance, the corresponding free vibration is low enough to be captured by the low-speed cameras. To ensure accurate deformation measurements, it is vital to apply a good speckle pattern. For this experiment, the speckle pattern was applied using the spray paint technique. First, a base coat of flat white paint was sprayed on the surface of the composite. Once dried, a thin black mist was applied to create the speckle pattern. This was accomplished by inverting the spray can and throttling the nozzle approximately 2 feet above the specimen. In doing so, a properly sized and spaced speckle pattern was customized for this experiment. All sides of the composite samples where cuts were made were also painted to prevent water intrusion into the sample.

3 Test Procedure

Initial testing was conducted in air to provide a baseline for comparison with all other conditions of testing. It is used to identify the differences in responses of the composite samples with FSI in water. For DIC testing, the beams were held in the cantilever testing apparatus. For the impact hammer testing the beam was held in a free-free condition with 6lb fishing line suspended from the ceiling with a rubber band link between each and loosely tied around the beam at its predicted first mode nodal points. Because composites may absorb moisture while testing in water, which affects the material behaviors, testing of the composites was conducted in air before and immediately after the tests submerged in water to ensure water intrusion did not occur affecting the composite samples. Comparing the two air test data showed that the results are the same confirming there was no water intrusion affecting the material properties.

The water tank was filled with approximately 70.4 liters of distilled water bringing the water level to 431.8mm above the bottom of the tank. For DIC testing the water level was 133.35mm above the tip of the composite beam after being placed in the support. The water level for the modal analysis was 215.9mm above the sample as it was suspended in the center of the water tank in its free-free condition. Using distilled water limited the amount of particles in the water that could adversely affect the images during DIC testing.

A standard three-point bend test was conducted to determine the bending stiffness EI in order to calculate the theoretical frequencies of the composite beams with the given boundary conditions. This test was conducted using all samples of each layer sequence. An *Instron* testing machine was utilized to measure and record force and deflection data. The bending stiffness was computed using Euler-Bernoulli beam theory, where the deflection of a simply supported beam with a span length L and a center-wise applied force P gives the maximum deflection δ as:

$$\delta = \frac{PL^3}{48EI} \quad (3)$$

Solving for the bending stiffness yields:

$$EI = \frac{PL^3}{48\delta} \quad (4)$$

In addition, the density ρ was obtained by measuring the mass m and volume V . Table 2 provides the bending stiffness of each beam as determined by the methods described, and the density is 1799 kg/m³.

In order to determine the camera settings for the DIC testing technique, the frequency of vibration must first be determined. The beam can be modeled as a continuous system in which its natural frequency is given in terms of a constant $\beta_n L$ corresponding to the normal modes of oscillation as below

$$f_n = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{\beta_n^4 EI}{\rho A}}; \quad n=1,2,3,\dots \quad (5)$$

where A is the cross-sectional area of the beam. Due to the addition of mass by the ten accelerometers, it is reasonable to expect that the experimental natural frequency will be lower than the theoretical natural frequency. Accounting for the mass of the ten

accelerometers, the density of the beam is modified by including the mass of accelerometers.

For modal analysis, the sampling rate of the dynamic signal analyzer was set to 500Hz which corresponds to 2ms and meets the Nyquist criterion [10]. Due to the inability to waterproof the impact hammer for testing in composite beams submerged in water, a six inch steel rod was held on the beam and tapped with the hammer to transfer the force to the beam. The rod was removed immediately after impact and prior to the rebound of the beam. Any test where the rebound resulted in contact with the rod was discarded and repeated.

The accuracy of this method was tested on an aluminum beam with dimensions of 279.4 x 25.4 x 6.35mm. It was outfitted with ten accelerometers evenly spaced along the centerline of the beam in the same way as the composite beams. First, the beam was struck with the impact hammer at the center of the end directly over the first accelerometer. This test consisted of five frames for averaging. A second test was conducted by striking the steel rod as it was held in the same location as the previous test. Again, five frames were represented for averaging. It appears that impacting a steel rod resting on the composite beam and removing it prior to rebound has little, if any, effect on the accurate vibration testing. Mode shapes are identical in both methods with less than a third of a percent difference in natural frequencies. With the validation of this method, it was utilized for all testing whether in air or in water to provide consistency among testing.

4 Results and Discussion

Initial testing in air was completed to provide a baseline for comparison with all other testing environments. Testing was then conducted in a water environment in order to determine changes in the response of free vibration. This was followed by more testing in air to show repeatability as well as to show that water intrusion into composite specimens is not a factor to be considered. Samples of each orientation with the fine speckle pattern were not used for analysis due to aliasing of the data. Figure 2 illustrates a representative sample of the displacement of the composite beam in the water environment as compared to its reference in air. This is used as a measure of validation in that acquiring images with the CCDs through a water medium is accurate when compared to images

acquired through an air medium. The tip of the beam was displaced 19.05mm which was measured along the length of the beam in both air and water environments. This measure consisted of 100 evenly spaced points along the centerline of the beam. As shown in Fig. 2, there is good agreement between the displacements in each of the testing environments. However, there is a slight discrepancy at the tip of the beam. There is a about a 2% difference in the tip displacements from each environment. This difference may be due to the distortion of the image at the tip caused by amplitude in the out-of-plane displacement.

The images taken by the HSC were used to determine the experimental natural frequency of the vibrating beams. The time was measured as a function of the frame rate, and then the damped natural frequency was computed from the time of period. Multiple periods were determined for each beam to improve the accuracy.

The experimental damping ratio was determined from the displacement-time plot. The undamped natural frequency was calculated from the damped natural frequency and the damping ratio. Table 3 compares the theoretical and experimental fundamental frequencies of the beam in air for the first mode. The theoretical values for natural frequency listed in the table were calculated using Eq. (5) with the dimensions of each beam. These values are in good agreement with the obtained experimental natural frequencies.

For the tests conducted in water, the average natural frequencies for the 0°/90° and ±45° samples are 4.92Hz and 3.58Hz, respectively. The ±45° samples again showed lower frequencies than the 0°/90° samples. The natural frequencies for the beams when tested in air are much higher than when tested in water. This is expected due to the added mass effect in FSI. On average, the added mass effect on the beams in a water environment decreases its natural frequency by around two thirds of those seen in an air environment. In other words, the frequencies of the composite beams in air are approximately three times greater than those in water.

Since a system under free vibration will vibrate at one or more of its natural frequencies, its response shape is described as the linear combination of mode shapes. In other words, the shape of which the beam takes on at an instance of time is seen as the

weighted sum of all mode shapes. Each natural frequency corresponds to a specific mode shape.

Since the initial displacement of the beam closely resembles the mode I shape, it is reasonable to expect that this shape will dominate in its free vibration response shape. Figures 3 and 4 are the free vibrational response shapes for E-glass composite beam in air and in water. Each line in the graphs is representative of the displacement along the length of the beam. The top graph in each figure corresponds to the first couple of seconds (i.e. early time) as the beam is in free vibration. The bottom graph corresponds to the remaining recorded time in two second intervals (i.e. late time).

It is apparent that mode I is the dominant shape for the first couple of seconds in the free vibration in Figs. 3 and 4. As time progresses, the response shape in air remains relatively the same as the mode I as shown in Fig. 3. There are minor ripples present in the dynamically deflected beam shapes, but the ripples are probably caused by noise in the system. In water, however, the result is much different. Figure 4 shows multiple peaks and valleys along the vibrational shapes of the beam at the various times. The response shape appears to remain the same throughout the test period, leading to the conclusion that this phenomenon results from FSI. That is, the composite beam in water has the vibrational response consisting of the dominant mode I and other higher modes. As time elapses, the dominant mode I dissipates quickly, and the higher modes show up distinctly at later times. If the hydrodynamic mass was applied uniformly to the beam resulting from FSI, the responses of the beam would be close each other in air or water except for the vibrating frequencies. Both $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}$ and $+45^{\circ}/-45^{\circ}$ composites showed the same characteristics when comparing the vibrations in air and water, respectively. However, the $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}$ composite gave a greater change with FSI.

Figures 5 and 6 shows the fringes of transverse displacements of the composite beam at later times in air and water, respectively. The higher mode effect with FSI is clearly seen in Fig. 6 which is consistent with that in Fig. 4.

The experimental modal analysis was conducted for a carbon-fiber composite beam. The same tests were conducted while the specimens were in air or in water to compare the FSI effect using the modal

testing. The beam was tested with the free-free boundary conditions.

Table 4 compares the natural frequencies of the composite beam in air and water, respectively. The FSI reduced the natural frequency by approximately 40%. When the mode shapes are compared for the composite beam in air and in water, there is a sizable difference as shown Fig. 7. It is mentioned that due to the lightness of the composite beam, some of these differences in mode shapes in air and in water could be attributed to more pronounced differences in the ability to effectively excite the beam using impact excitation. This is because the relatively low inertia of the beam made it more difficult to impart energy through an impact. This effect was more pronounced in air than in water, due to the added mass in water. It is noted that the coherence function was monitored during the collection of all frequency response functions, and was very good to excellent in all cases. The curvatures of all three modes are quite different for the composite beams tested in air and water, respectively, as shown in Fig. 8. The largest difference occurs in the first and second modes of the composite beam, which is the case for the aluminum beam.

The modal curvature is the second derivative of the mode shape. That means, while the mode shape is associated with the beam deflection, the modal curvature is related to bending strain of the beam. This result supports the finding in the previous impact testing on beam and plate structures in air and water, respectively [13, 14]. The measured strains in air and water show drastic differences from strain gage location to location.

5. Conclusions

This study was conducted to gain a better understanding of polymer composite materials used in marine applications under conditions in which FSI occurs. The DIC, HSP, and EMA were used for the study. As expected, the added mass effect of FSI reduced natural frequencies of the beams when they are in water compared to those in air. Since the E-glass composite has the lowest density, the reduction in natural frequencies due to FSI is the largest with 50% while the carbon composite has a reduction of 40%. All the comparisons were made with free-free beams.

The FSI also influenced the mode shapes. The effect on the mode shapes was measurable for the carbon composite beam. The FSI influenced more significantly the curvatures of the mode shapes. The degree of influence varies from mode to mode. In general, the first and second modal curvatures have large differences between the air and wet tests. The difference in modal curvatures is important because the bending strain is directly related to the modal curvature rather than the mode shape. The test results explain why the difference in strains measured for composite plates under impact loading between in air and water, respectively, varied from location to location of the plate [7,8].

Free vibrational responses of E-glass composite beams showed that FSI activates high frequency modal components in the vibration. As a result, the beam submerged in water has more transverse motions along span not correlated with a first mode shape even though the beam was excited with the initial deformed shape very close to the first modal shape.

The results of this study show the significance of the added mass effect of FSI on dynamic behaviors of polymer composites which is due to their densities being comparable to the density of water. The FSI can shift the critical failure location in composite structures because it affects the modal curvatures significantly, which was observed in a previous study.

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Figure 3. Free vibrations shapes in air for $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}$ composite beam (top: early time, bottom: late time)

Figure 4. Free vibrations shapes in air for $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}$ composite beam (top: early time, bottom: late time)

Figure 5. Contour plot of transverse displacements along the length of the cantilever beam in air at 2.8s after initial displacement for E-glass composite beam with $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}$ lamination

Figure 6. Contour plot of transverse displacements along the length of the cantilever beam in water at 2.4s after initial displacement for E-glass composite beam with $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}$ lamination

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Figure 7. Comparison of mode shapes of free-free carbon composite beam in air and water

Figure 8. Comparison of modal curvatures of free-free carbon composite beam in air and water